

Formation Control of Underactuated Autonomous Surface Vessels Using Redundant Manipulator Analogs

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Abstract- In this paper, we present a method utilizing redundant manipulator analogs for formation control of underactuated autonomous surface vessels (ASVs) with realistic turning constraints and dynamics. The method used relies on casting the swarm as a single entity and utilizing redundant manipulator techniques to guarantee task-level formation control as well as obstacle avoidance and secondary tasks such as mean position control. The method presented differs from other approaches in that the units herein represent a larger class of ASVs with realistic limitations on vessel motions and that the exact position of each of the units on the formation profile is not specified.

I. INTRODUCTION

Controller development for effective cooperation among units in swarms of robotic systems requires significant care. A great deal of effort has been directed at developing centralized and decentralized control strategies for a wide variety of swarming applications [1,2,3,4,5,6,7]. Many efforts have focused on formation control, including [8 - 12].

In [8], the authors utilize the basic formulation from [1] and [2] to develop a formation controller for groups of underactuated autonomous surface vessels. In this work, we develop a controller that admits a wider class of realistic ASVs and enables flexible formation control under which the units are able to adjust their positions on a specified formation curve while achieving secondary objectives. To do so, we rely on methods from [13, 14] to develop a novel controller for swarms of underactuated surface vessels. The proposed controller has the following characteristics:

- i) Admits realistic hydrodynamics for underactuated nonholonomic vessels. The system accommodates units with both nonzero turning radius (a common characteristic of single-screw and rudder designs as opposed to differential thrust or dual-screw designs) and increased resistance beyond hull speed, as is common for displacement vessels.
- ii) Admits any smooth formation profile.
- iii) Allows local adjustment of relative position of units on the swarm formation profile to achieve secondary objectives.
- iv) Provides for reactive control with only swarm-level path planning

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In addition to the added motion realism mentioned previously, the work shown in this paper differs from that of [8] as well as [13, 14] in several key ways. In [8], the authors select a rigid formation for the units, while in this work we select a formation *shape* and use the controller to force the units to converge to a formation that lies on that shape profile but does not have *a priori* fixed unit locations. In this way, the work is more closely related to that of [17, 18], although with a centralized approach that accommodates additional dynamics. While the work in [13, 14] forms the basis for the control, the application of these concepts to flexible formations is entirely novel. This work forms an important basis for ongoing studies in cooperative surface vessel tactics for dynamic environments.

The remainder of the paper is organized as follows. In Section II, we discuss the problem statement and the assumptions on swarm composition and dynamics, including the minimum turn radius and nonlinear powering effects (hull speed). In Section III, we define the control method that is used to achieve swarm control. Section IV includes a simulation study demonstrating the efficacy of the system. Finally, we offer conclusions and some ideas for future work in Section V.

II. PROBLEM STATEMENT

A. Vehicle Dynamics and Kinematics

In this paper, we will consider control of a swarm of n cooperating vehicles with dynamics and kinematics that approximate a wide class of autonomous surface vessels (ASVs). The model that we will use includes full system dynamics as well as limitations on available torque and turning radius required to produce a realistic motion profile for ships equipped with a single screw for thrust and a rudder for yaw moment generation.

The dynamics of our prototypical system for unit $\#i$ in a swarm are given in (1) - (8) and illustrated in Figure 1. This model was adapted from [8] and [9], and our swarm will admit the inclusion of heterogeneous resources, so that all of the vessels need not have identical parameters.

Figure 1: Autonomous Surface Vessel Model

$$\eta_i = \begin{bmatrix} x_i \\ y_i \\ \theta_i \end{bmatrix} \text{ and } v_i = \begin{bmatrix} u_i \\ v_i \\ \dot{\theta}_i \end{bmatrix} \quad (1)$$

$$\dot{\eta}_i = R(\theta_i)v_i \quad (2)$$

$$R(\theta_i) = \begin{bmatrix} \cos(\theta_i) & -\sin(\theta_i) & 0 \\ \sin(\theta_i) & \cos(\theta_i) & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \quad (3)$$

$$M_i \dot{v}_i + (C_i + D_i(v_i))v_i = \begin{bmatrix} \tau_{i1} \\ 0 \\ \tau_{i3} \end{bmatrix} \quad (4)$$

$$M_i = \begin{bmatrix} m_{i11} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & m_{i22} & m_{i23} \\ 0 & m_{i32} & m_{i33} \end{bmatrix} \quad (5)$$

$$D_i = \begin{bmatrix} d_{i11} + d_{i11}^n |u_i| & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & d_{i22} & d_{i23} \\ 0 & d_{i32} & d_{i33} \end{bmatrix} \quad (6)$$

$$C_i = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & c_{i23} \\ 0 & c_{i32} & 0 \end{bmatrix} \quad (7)$$

$$q_\eta = \begin{bmatrix} \eta_1 \\ \vdots \\ \eta_n \end{bmatrix} \quad (8)$$

where i is the index of unit $\#i$ in the swarm and

- (x_i, y_i) is the location of the center of gravity vessel
- L_i is the total length
- L_{cg_i} is the distance from the CG to the bow
- u_i is the *surge speed* of the vessel in its body frame
- v_i is the *sway speed* in the body frame
- θ_i is the yaw angle in the world coordinate frame
- τ_{i1} is the thrust generated by the prime mover
- τ_{i3} is the yaw torque generated by the rudder system
- M_i is the inertial matrix for vessel i
- D_i is the damping matrix for vessel i
- C_i are terms representing the Coriolis forces
- q_η is the full, concatenated state of the swarm

This is an underactuated system, where the two control inputs (thrust τ_{i1} and rudder-generated yaw torque τ_{i3}) control three state variables (u_i, v_i, θ_i) through a nonlinear relationship. The result of this underactuation is a nonholonomic constraint, limiting the achievable velocities of the system.

B. Hydrodynamics

In this work, we are concerned with surface vessels operating in displacement mode, wherein the primary forces supporting the weight of the vessel arise from buoyancy. This type of vessel has a powering profile that is highly nonlinear as speed in the water increases beyond a specific point. That point is the *hull speed* of the vessel, which is primarily determined by length and hullform. Vessels of this sort are significantly more efficient when moving forward than when moving backward, so we will limit the system to non-negative surge speed.

For efficient use of ASVs, it is important that the system not attempt to push units past their hull speed unless it is absolutely mission essential. As such, we will limit the torque τ_{i1} such that the acceleration of the vessel in the surge direction is non-positive definite when the vessel is at or above hull speed. Coupled with the forward motion constraint, we have the following limit on velocity, where s_i is the hull speed for the i -th ASV:

$$0 \leq u_i \leq s_i \quad (9)$$

This translates to:

$$\tau_{i1} \begin{cases} \leq 0 & \text{when } u_i \geq s_i \\ \geq 0 & \text{when } u_i \leq 0 \end{cases} \quad (10)$$

Finally, to accommodate the turning circle kinematics of a vessel, we limit acceleration when the yaw rate and surge speed define a turn radius that is equal to the ship's turning circle radius (R_{tc}^i). That is, we enforce the following limit on yaw rate:

$$|\dot{\theta}_i| \leq \frac{|u_i|}{R_{tc}^i} \quad (11)$$

This is a significant constraint, and must be accommodated in the vessel control and in the coordination controller.

C. Task Model

In this work, we will consider controlling a swarm of vessels executing a formation in the presence of obstacles and under the hydrodynamic constraints discussed in the previous section. We want our formation to be flexible in the sense that the units will reach a specified shape profile, but the exact location of each unit on that profile or relative to any other unit is not specified but rather is generated by the secondary tasks of the system, such as obstacle avoidance and mean position of the swarm.

We formulate the primary task for the system as follows:

$$V(q) = \sum_{i=1}^n \rho(\eta_i) \quad (12)$$

where $\rho(\eta_i)$ is the square of the minimum distance from unit $\#i$ to the formation profile, defining the individual unit accomplishment of the formation. The overall task is to get $V(q)$ to 0 while not colliding with obstacles or other units. For control purposes, we define $\rho(\eta_i)$ not from the center of the vessel, but from the bow, which we define as a control point p_i (as seen in Figure 1).

$$p_i = \begin{bmatrix} x_{cp_i} \\ y_{cp_i} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} x_i \\ y_i \end{bmatrix} + L_{cg_i} \begin{bmatrix} \cos(\theta_i) \\ \sin(\theta_i) \end{bmatrix} \quad (13)$$

III. CONTROL SYSTEM

The complete controller for the task discussed in Section II includes several components. The controller is defined as follows:

A. Formation Specification

We characterize the desired formation using a 2D planar curve and a motion profile. For this work, we do not consider time-varying formation profile shape, only formations that translate according to a motion profile:

$$f(x - x_f(t), y - y_f(t)) = 0 \quad (14)$$

where $(x_f(t), y_f(t))$ is the overall trajectory of the formation.

B. System state for control

We define a control state of the system as

$$q = [x_{cp_1} \ y_{cp_1} \ \dots \ x_{cp_n} \ y_{cp_n}] = [p_1^T \ \dots \ p_n^T]^T \quad (15)$$

C. Primary task Jacobian

We define the Jacobian relating unit control point velocities to task-space velocities:

$$J_{ti} = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{\partial V(q)}{\partial x_{cp_i}} & \frac{\partial V(q)}{\partial y_{cp_i}} \end{bmatrix} \quad (16)$$

$$J_t = [J_{t1} \ \dots \ J_{tn}] \quad (17)$$

where the task-level function is the sum of the square of the formation value for each unit:

$$V(q) = \sum_{i=1}^n (f(x_i, y_i))^2 \quad (18)$$

$V(q)$ will be zero iff all units are on the function profile. An example is given in Section IV.B.

D. Task space controller

We utilize a proportional task-space controller to determine the desired control point velocities and accelerations for the primary task (recalling that the formation function $V(q)$ will be zero when the units are all on the profile):

$$\dot{q}_{main}^d = J_t^+ \left(K_t (-V(q)) + \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 \\ \vdots & \vdots \\ 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \dot{x}_f(t) \\ \dot{y}_f(t) \end{bmatrix} \right) \quad (19)$$

where K_t is a gain, the right-hand term represents the feedforward velocity of the moving formation, and J_t^+ is the pseudoinverse of the task Jacobian, given by:

$$J_t^+ = J_t^T (J_t J_t^T)^{-1} \quad (20)$$

E. Obstacle Avoidance

We accommodate obstacle and unit avoidance using an artificial potential field method to generate avoidance vectors. The inter-unit repulsion field for the system is given by

$$\begin{bmatrix} \dot{q}_{avoid_vessel}^d(2i-1) \\ \dot{q}_{avoid_vessel}^d(2i) \end{bmatrix} = \sum_{\substack{j=1:n \\ j \neq i}} \begin{cases} \left| \frac{1}{\| (p_i - p_j) \| - L_i} - \frac{1}{\rho} \right| \frac{(p_i - p_j)}{\| (p_i - p_j) \|} & \text{when } \| (p_i - p_j) \| < \rho \\ 0 & \text{when } \| (p_i - p_j) \| \geq \rho \end{cases} \quad (21)$$

where ρ is the maximum distance for effect from the inter-vessel repulsion. For obstacle avoidance we use a similar composition:

$$\begin{bmatrix} \dot{q}_{avoid_obst}^d(2i-1) \\ \dot{q}_{avoid_obst}^d(2i) \end{bmatrix} = \begin{cases} \left| \frac{1}{\| d_i \| - L_i} - \frac{1}{\rho_{obst}} \right| \frac{d_i}{\| d_i \|} & \text{when } \| d_i \| < \rho_{obst} \\ 0 & \text{when } \| d_i \| \geq \rho_{obst} \end{cases} \quad (22)$$

where d_i is the vector from the closest obstacle point to the control point of vessel i and ρ_{obst} is the radius of effect of the obstacle repulsive field.

The complete avoidance vector is the sum of the two avoidance terms.

$$\dot{q}_{avoid}^d = \dot{q}_{avoid_vessel}^d + \dot{q}_{avoid_obst}^d \quad (23)$$

The task-space control point velocities generated will be projected onto the null space of the primary task Jacobian in the final coordination controller. While it is possible to make obstacle avoidance primary, as in [2, 8], we choose here to project the avoidance vector onto the high-dimensional null-space of the system. When obstacle avoidance is not compatible with the formation objective we can promote the avoidance aspect to primary. This situation is simple to detect by looking for vanishing null-space projections of the avoidance vector. Switching in this manner must be done using hysteresis to avoid chattering, but experiments have shown that such cases are rare. Thus, under normal operation, the primary objectives drive the evolution of the swarm configuration, providing better convergence of the swarm to the formation profile in the presence of obstacles.

F. Mean Position Control

We accommodate mean position control by defining a further Jacobian:

$$\begin{bmatrix} \bar{x}_{cp} \\ \bar{y}_{cp} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n x_{cp_i} \\ \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n y_{cp_i} \end{bmatrix} \quad (24)$$

$$\begin{bmatrix} \dot{\bar{x}}_{cp} \\ \dot{\bar{y}}_{cp} \end{bmatrix} = J_{mean} \dot{q} \quad (25)$$

$$J_{mean} = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{1}{n} & 0 & \dots & \frac{1}{n} & 0 \\ 0 & \frac{1}{n} & \dots & 0 & \frac{1}{n} \end{bmatrix} \quad (26)$$

Then, we select the secondary task space velocity based on a simple proportional control:

$$\dot{q}_{mean}^d = J_{mean}^+ \left(K_p \left(\begin{bmatrix} \bar{x}_{cp} \\ \bar{y}_{cp} \end{bmatrix}^d - \begin{bmatrix} \bar{x}_{cp} \\ \bar{y}_{cp} \end{bmatrix} \right) \right) \quad (27)$$

where J_{mean}^+ is the pseudoinverse of J_{mean} , K_p is a gain and the superscript d indicates the desired value.

G. Control Point Desired Velocity

Preliminary desired control point velocities are now computed using the redundant manipulator analog:

$$\dot{q}^d = \dot{q}_{main}^d + K_a (I - J_t^+ J_t) \dot{q}_{avoid}^d + (I - J_t^+ J_t) (I - GG^T) \dot{q}_{mean}^d \quad (28)$$

where J_t^+ is the pseudoinverse of J_t , as in (18), K_a is a gain and G is $2n \times 1$ matrix given by:

$$\hat{r}(i) = \begin{bmatrix} \dot{q}_{avoid}^d(2i-1) \\ \dot{q}_{avoid}^d(2i) \end{bmatrix} \text{ for } i \in [1, n] \quad (29)$$

$$\begin{bmatrix} G(2i-1) \\ G(2i) \end{bmatrix} = \frac{\hat{r}(i)}{\|\hat{r}(i)\|} \text{ if } \|\hat{r}(i)\| > 0, \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} \text{ otherwise} \quad (30)$$

This definition of G allows us to project the mean control vector onto the null space of the avoidance vector, which is then projected onto the null space of the primary task, as in [1]. By our definition of G , obstacles have no effect on the mean position controller when they are outside of their radius of influence.

H. Computation of Achievable Desired Velocities

We limit the commanded accelerations to accommodate the known vessel dynamics. As our control arises from desired velocities for control points, we modify the computed values to match the known constraints on vessel motion (turn radius and hull speed). Thus, we enforce the hard velocity limits from section II.B and select the achievable velocity that is closest to the desired velocity in magnitude and direction.

To accommodate the highly nonholonomic system, we choose to also limit desired speed based on the difference between the desired heading and the actual heading of each vessel. That is, after computing the desired velocity for the control point, we scale the magnitude of that velocity following the work of [8], albeit with a slightly more generous scale. This prevents the system from generating large thrust when the vessel is pointed away from its target heading, which results in more controllable motion and smaller excursions:

$$\dot{q}_i^d = [\dot{q}^d(2i-1), \dot{q}^d(2i)]^T \quad (31)$$

$$\|\dot{q}_i^d\| := \frac{(2+\cos(\gamma_i))}{3} \|\dot{q}_i^d\| \quad (32)$$

where

$$\gamma_i = \tan^{-1} \left(\frac{\dot{q}_i^d(2)}{\dot{q}_i^d(1)} \right) - \theta_i \quad (33)$$

If we did nothing else, the system performance would degrade significantly under the limitations imposed. However, in [14], we developed a methodology for reactive control of nonholonomic swarms using local capability redistribution. The fundamental technique applied in that work accommodates any deviation between a desired and achievable unit motion. This iterative method is outlined below for completeness, and consists of redistributing effort across the null space of the primary task when a unit's computed desired velocity is not achievable:

- Compute \dot{q}^d
- Set $v_{corr}(i) = 0, i \in [1, \dots, 2n]$
- Repeat for max number of rejections or until all velocities are achievable
 - Compute $v_{corr} = \dot{q}^{best} - \dot{q}^d$ where \dot{q}^{best} is the

achievable velocity for the system closest to \dot{q}^d

- Reproject error: $\dot{q}^d := \dot{q}^d + (I - J_t^+ J_t)(v_{corr})$
- Apply nonholonomic constraints and limitations to new \dot{q}^d

I. Torque Generation

Now that we have an achievable \dot{q}^d , we use the computed torque method common in robot control to generate the torque commands for all units, noting that there is no achievable torque in the sway direction.

We first need to relate task space control point velocities \dot{q} to body-frame velocities v_i .

$$\dot{q} = J_b v \quad (34)$$

where

$$J_{b_i} = \begin{bmatrix} \cos(\theta_i) & -\sin(\theta_i) & -\frac{L_{cg_i}}{2} \sin(\theta_i) \\ \sin(\theta_i) & \cos(\theta_i) & \frac{L_{cg_i}}{2} \cos(\theta_i) \end{bmatrix} \quad (35)$$

with

$$J_b = \begin{bmatrix} J_{b_1} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \ddots & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & J_{b_n} \end{bmatrix} \quad (36)$$

We can now define our complete controller:

$$a = K_d(\dot{q}^d - \dot{q}) \quad (37)$$

$$\tau = H(M J_b^+(a - \dot{J}_b v) + (C + D(v))v) \quad (38)$$

where J_b^+ is the pseudoinverse of J_b , as in (20), matrices M , C and D are block diagonal concatenations of the individual M_i , C_i , and D_i matrices, K_d is the final system gain, and H is a matrix that enforces the underactuation constraint that comes from the fact that we cannot apply force in the sway direction:

$$H = \begin{bmatrix} h_1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \ddots & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & h_n \end{bmatrix} \text{ with } h_i = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \quad (39)$$

Finally, as the simulated system (4) does not include the full nonlinear dynamics of the vessels, we guarantee a realistic simulation by enforcing the turning radius constraint at the acceleration level based on (11).

IV. SIMULATIONS

In this section, we present a simulation that exercises all of the primary aspects of the control for a homogeneous system of five vessels whose basic dynamic parameters were adopted from [9], but with added nonholonomic constraints that match those discussed in Section II. We note that the system has been used successfully on a variety of circular and elliptical formations as well as heterogeneous systems, details of which have been excluded for brevity.

A. Dynamics and constraints

Each unit has identical dynamics for our simulation, although this is not required:

$$M_i = \begin{bmatrix} 180.3 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 2.436 & 1.3095 \\ 0 & 1.3095 & 172.2 \end{bmatrix} \times 10^6$$

$$c_{i23} = -c_{i32} = 8.61 \times 10^6$$

$$D_i = \begin{bmatrix} 3.883 \times 10^{-9} - 2.393 \times 10^{-9} |u_i| & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0.2181 & -3.434 \\ 0 & 3.706 & 26.54 \end{bmatrix} \times 10^6$$

$$L_i = 33 \text{ meters}$$

$$L_{c_{g_i}} = 19.5 \text{ meters}$$

We also set limits on hull speed and turning circle radius:

$$s_i = 7.17 \frac{m}{s}$$

$$R_{tc}^i = 33 \text{ meters}$$

B. Simulation Parameters

Initial conditions:

Zero initial velocity

$$[\eta_1(0) \ \eta_2(0) \ \eta_3(0) \ \eta_4(0) \ \eta_5(0)] = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 50 & -100 & 100 & 150 \\ 100 & 0 & -50 & -100 & 50 \\ \pi/4 & -\pi/2 & \pi & 0 & \pi/8 \end{bmatrix}$$

Formation and task specifications:

Angled parabola:

$$\begin{bmatrix} x_{\sigma_i} \\ y_{\sigma_i} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \cos(\sigma) & \sin(\sigma) \\ -\sin(\sigma) & \cos(\sigma) \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} x_{cp_i} - (100 + 4t) \\ y_{cp_i} - 50 \end{bmatrix}$$

$$f(x_{cp_i}, y_{cp_i}) = (x_{\sigma_i}) + \frac{1}{100} (y_{\sigma_i})^2$$

$$V(q) = \sum_{i=1}^5 (f(x_{cp_i}, y_{cp_i}))^2$$

$$J_{t_i} = 2f(x_i, y_i) \begin{bmatrix} \cos(\sigma) - \frac{2y_{\sigma_i}}{100} \sin(\sigma) & \sin(\sigma) + \frac{2y_{\sigma_i}}{100} \cos(\sigma) \end{bmatrix}$$

$$\begin{bmatrix} \bar{x}_{cp} \\ \bar{y}_{cp} \end{bmatrix}^d = \begin{bmatrix} (100 + 4t) - 125 \cos(\sigma) \\ 50 - 125 \sin(\sigma) \end{bmatrix}$$

$$\sigma = 3\pi/4$$

Controller Gains and Parameters:

$K_t = 10$, $\rho = \rho_{obst} = 3L$, $K_a = 1000$, $K_p = 0.1$, $K_d = 8$, maximum number of reprojections: 10

Obstacles

Two circular obstacles placed at $[x, y] = [500, -100]m$ and $[x, y] = [1000, -100]m$, each with radius of 50 meters.

C. Results

Results of the simulations are shown in Figure 2 - Figure 6. Figure 2 shows the trace of the CGs for each vessel for no velocity reprojection as well as for 10 iterations of that algorithm. Of note is the smooth nature of the motion and the limited turn radius, especially obvious in the unit that begins at the leftmost point in the plot (unit #3, which begins pointing along the negative x axis). Snapshots showing local maneuvering are given in Figure 3, with the steady-state swarm formation shown in Figure 4. The final swarm pose and unit spacing was dictated not *a priori*, but as an

emergent formation influenced by the initial conditions, the environment, and the inter-unit repulsion as well as the desired mean position.

Figure 2: CG (not control point) location traces for swarm with 10 reprojections (solid lines) and 0 reprojections (dashed lines).

Figure 3: Selected swarm snapshots (10 reprojections). Desired formation profile is in blue, with target (x) and actual (o) mean position.

Figure 4: Open-water steady-state formation. All units have control points on the formation and that the mean position is at the target value.

Performance measures are shown in Figure 5 for the main task and Figure 6 for the mean position control. Performance on the primary task shows excellent error convergence after an initial transient associated with the nonholonomic nature of the units. Note that since the mean position control is projected onto the null space of the

obstacle avoidance, mean position is not guaranteed when near obstacles or when the vessels are tightly packed.

As seen in the performance curves, the system gives up some ability to achieve the secondary objective in order to achieve better convergence on the primary task during the initial transient. However, the rejections do not affect steady-state performance of the mean tracking system, and maximum excursion post-convergence is decreased.

Figure 5: (a) Value of $V(q)$ for 10 rejections. (b) difference between $V(q)$ for a maximum of 10 rejections and 0 rejections (negative value indicates that the projected controller better meets the primary task).

Figure 6: Error in swarm mean for 10 and 0 rejections.

V. CONCLUSION

In this work, we have presented a flexible formation controller for swarms of cooperating autonomous surface vessels with realistic dynamics and additional motion constraints that match a large group of vessels with one screw and one rudder. The reported system is novel in that it admits a larger class of ASV dynamics and kinematics than previous approaches using the same basic control formulation. Further, our system allows for emergent unit placement on the formation profile with secondary objectives, while the work in [8] relies on *a priori* vessel location specification. The simulated system attains a rotated parabola formation while achieving obstacle avoidance and mean position objectives, but any formation profile is accommodated and a wide range of additional objectives may be implemented.

Limitations of the current system include that the controller is centralized, requiring robust communication and accurate global state knowledge. Future work involves the use of these methods for swarms in dynamic

environments, wherein we will allow the environmental factors such as sea state, current and wind to influence not only the positions of the units on the formation profile, but the formation profile itself. We will also consider methods for decentralization based on the work in [16, 17, 18].

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